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Sea Pirates and Socio-economic Development in Nigeria: A Study of the Rivers State, 2013 – 2023

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ABSTRACT

The paper examined sea piracy and socio-economic development in Nigeria with a focus on Rivers State, 2013 - 2023. The study adopted three objectives which investigated among others the causes and impact of sea piracy on socioeconomic development, and socioeconomic effect of sea piracy in Rivers State. The rational choice theory was adopted as its theoretical construct. The population of the study consisted of boat operators and waterways users in Abonnema, Abuloma, Bonny, Okrika and ATC jetties around Rivers State. Using random sampling method, fifty respondents from each of the selected routes were selected for the study, thus bringing the sample size to 250. Data were analysed using the simple percentage statistical method. Findings revealed among others that get-rich-quick syndrome, years of neglect, economic marginalization and struggle for political power were causes of sea piracy while increased in crime rate, poor patronage of sea transportation, and business handicap were significant socioeconomic effect of sea piracy. The paper recommended among others that efforts should be made to reform maritime policy toward protecting life and property. Also, death penalty should be prescribed for any pirate practices as part of sea policy as this would discourage terror and enhance water ways or blue economy.

Keywords: Piracy, Sea Piracy, Economic, Socioeconomic, Development

INTRODUCTION

Piracy is fast becoming an issue of great concern as it is a threat to national security, economic prosperity, and protection of lives and properties of merchants (Otubor, 2019). For a long time, pirates operating in different parts of the globe have held the world shipping community hostage, threatened the economies of many countries, and relegated efforts to protect lives and citizens by many countries fruitless. This resulted to the International Maritime Bureau (IMB), raising alarm to all maritime nations to take drastic actions against the menace. It was one call that the world responded to, including Nigeria and the rest of West African states which early this year were classified as dangerous as Somalia where pirates have made sailing unsafe for ship owners and crew on board (Onuoha, 2012). Jesugbamila (2010) observed that the statistics compiled and reported by the IMB shows a ten percent increase in reported incidents of piracy worldwide. Alessi (2012) further reported a total of 439 piracy attacks worldwide in 2011, more

than half of which were attributed to Somali pirates operating in the Gulf of Aden, the Red Sea, the Arabian Sea, the Indian Ocean, and off the coast of Oman.

According to Sofiri, Nyiagaana and Jack (2022), sea piracy is a global issue that deals primarily with sea crimes such as robbery, hostage taking and disruption of economic activities through the sea. They noted that Rivers State has experienced its own share of this issue. He stressed that Rivers State was created on May 27, 1967, out of the defunct Eastern Region of Nigeria, with Port Harcourt as its capital. A section of the original Rivers State was later cut off in 1996 to form Bayelsa State. The state is made up of twenty-three (23) local government areas. It occupies an area of 11,077 km² and is bounded on the south by the Atlantic Ocean, to the west Bayelsa and Delta states, to the east by Akwa Ibom State, and to the north by Imo and Abia states. A predominantly low-lying pluvial state, its inland part consists of tropical rainforest and freshwater swamps and towards the coast, many mangrove swamps as well as coastal sand ridges. With a population estimate of over seven million people (NPS, 2015). According to him, the State is home to many ethnic nationalities including the Ikwerre, Ijaw, Ndoni, Ogoni, Etche, Ekpeye amongst others, who predominantly rely on fishing, farming, and mangrove forest harvesting as means of traditional livelihoods. Rivers State is host to critical oil and gas infrastructure in Nigeria and has over the last six decades remained a significant contributor of revenues to the socio-economic stability as well as the development of the country. The state's economic prowess which has earned it the enviable status as the nerve centre and capital of Nigeria's petroleum industry has catapulted its relevance in the political landscape of the country over the last two decades.

The socio-economic and political gains associated with its enviable status have also attracted a plethora of associated negative consequences ranging from widespread environmental pollution arising from oil and gas exploration to different forms of environmental conflicts and political violence that are often exacerbated by resources-based competition and agitations by armed militia groups. During the last two decades, Rivers State has been confronted with different forms of social conflicts and complex security challenges. In the mid-2000s, militancy marked by the struggle for resource control and self-determination significantly defined the security landscape of the state as it was in the rest of the Rivers State. The state became an epicenter for armed militia agitations with groups such as the Niger Delta People's Volunteer Force (NDPVF), the Niger Delta Vigilante (NDV), and the Movement for Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), who launched guerilla-styled attacks on critical oil infrastructure.

During this era, actors emerged as the major militant leaders and actors in the state as the introduction of the Presidential Amnesty Programme (PAP) by the Umaru Musa Yar'adua led Federal Government in the Niger Delta in 2009 saw a fundamental shift from oil militancy to other forms of insecurity in the state, including grassroots-based armed cult groups in local communities, intensified violent kidnapping, electoral violence, oil theft, and artisanal refining. Ten years into the implementation of the Presidential Amnesty Programme (PAP), the state experienced what could be described as a resurgence of cult violence, kidnapping, and armed robbery activities that almost brought the economy of the state to its knees. Most communities in Ikwerre, Ogoni, Andoni, Etche, and Emohua were overwhelmed by cult violence and kidnapping. The East-West Road, particularly the Emohua area up to the Rumuekpe Junction, were practically made impassable due to the activities of armed robbers and kidnappers despite the presence and proximity of heavily armed military and police personnel at various checkpoints on that road. This was also the case with the Elele Alimini axis of the Owerri-Port Harcourt Road where commercial buses filled with passengers were frequently hijacked and commuters abducted for ransom. In some cases, abducted passengers would be raped (Otubor, 2019). This was the pathetic situation of both passengers and commercial drivers on these two major roads before the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area (ONELGA) Security and Peace Advisory Committee (OSPAC), a government-backed local vigilante group, emerged to restore order and security in the area.

Theoretical Framework

The study adopts the Rational Choice Theory (RCT) propounded by Adam Smith when he captured it in his essay "*An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations*," from 1776. The book

proposed human nature's tendency toward self-interest resulted in prosperity. He used the work of Philosopher Thomas Hobbes' "*Leviathan*" (1651) to influence his own work. Moving from economics to the social sciences, in the 1950s and 1960s, sociologists George C. Homans, Peter Blau and James Coleman promoted rational choice theory in relation to social exchange. However, the theory was popularized by Ronald V. Clarke and Derek B. Cornish in 1986 in their book, "*The Reasoning Criminal: Rational Choice Perspectives on Offending*". The theory has been known as structural choice theory by Cohen, Kluegel and Land in 1981. It gained popularity in the fields of social sciences and has been constantly used to analyse social phenomena. The theory was used in the "*Analysis of Social Character, Behaviour and Socio-economic Activities*" by Miethe and Meier in 1993. They opined that rational choice theory expresses that individuals are in control of their decisions. They don't make choices because of unconscious drives, tradition or environmental influences. They use rational considerations to weigh consequences and potential benefits of their intended decision or action. According to them, the following assumptions are made.

- a. all actions are rational and are made due to considering costs and rewards.
- b. the reward of a relationship or action must outweigh the cost for the action to be completed.
- c. when the value of the reward diminishes below the value of the costs incurred, the person will stop the action or end the relationship.
- d. individuals will use the resources at their disposal to optimize their rewards.

Gongs, Famave, Maxwell and Annagu (2021) highlighted certain important conditions that drive crime as the desire or inordinate choice of the perpetrators of crimes, physical proximity of victims to motivated offenders, exposure of victims to a high-risk environment, attractiveness of suitable targets, and the absence of capable guardianship. Tayler (1997) states that the rationale behind the theory is that people will commit a crime if it is in their own best interests. sea piracy is a crime of opportunity of predatory victimisation, in which victims are not accidentally marked as targets. This suggests that, sea piracy is not a haphazard predation of random individuals. It is premeditated victimisation that involves intelligence and calculable approaches to acquiring suitable targets without being foiled. Thus, sea piracy in whatever form is situated within a criminal opportunity structure aimed at yielding desired intention for a motivated abductors and their accessories. A close look at the theory revealed that before kidnap targets are acquired, there must be physical proximity of suitable and attractive targets, and motivated kidnapper or sponsors. Attractive victims must be exposed via routine activities, such as using the waterways to travel, doing business, going to school, church, cinema, or visiting relatives at particular periods and there must be lack of capable security around targets. This forms the socio-spatial context where sea piracy of attractive victims is possible. This model views sea piracy as crime of opportunity, as such, victims serve as a means to an end, as envisaged by ransom, political, religious among other forms of sea piracy.

The implication of the theory for the study is that delinquent or criminal behaviour like sea piracy thrives well in a disorganized society. The theory posits that certain environment or geographical area especially towns or cities are prone to criminal behaviour including sea piracy. This is as a result of many years of neglect by oil companies causing degradation with their official collaborators to cause poverty on the people and leave their environment unclean thereby destroying the livelihood of the people because of the economic and social potentials of the area. Social change induced by personal choice, government/political policy, industrialization and urbanization, have precipitated sea piracy in the cities, towns and creek/waterways of Rivers State. This theory is relevant to this study because it laid bare the fact that the sea piracy as a crime is a decision undertaken by an individual whose desire or interest is fixed even if the nature of multinational oil companies operating in the Rivers State and the roles of the ruling political class is related to the exploitative nature of the capitalist system. It is the deliberate decision or choice of the pirates to embark on sea piracy and carry out transaction which enabled economically advanced countries to buy cheap stolen crude oil from coastal areas in Nigeria. This informs the pattern of rational choice decision and social interaction that pre-dispose sea pirates or individuals to circumstances that result to sea crimes.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Sea Piracy

Piracy have been viewed as a global crime, piracy that directly threatens the economic activities at sea the lives and lives of seafarers, strongly impacts maritime activity as well as economic development as noted by Burruss (2018). The global damage caused by piracy is estimated at \$ 6.6 to \$ 6.9 billion through commercial fraud, loss of cargo or delay. pirates are capable of causing political instability due to state officials' corruption. Technically, piracy has often been portraying as a business model and viewed as an activity that is primarily economically motivated (Nwalozie, 2020). While piracy assures revenues to the people involved in it, a direct causal association between poverty or lack of employment opportunities and piracy cannot be constructed. Rather than poverty per se, the critical issue is economic dislocation. Pirates are acts of loot taking place on the sea or the coast and are acted upon by illegal sea forces. People engage in piracy have discovered to be those who are economically marginalized and by virtue of their status have been put at a disadvantage by economic developments and globalization processes or are not allowed to participate in sources of wealth. Though piracy among other factors considered as a threat to maritime security, can be seen as an exemplary one. Piracy shows that maritime security threats have a propensity to be sticky. Given the fact that once it emerges, eradicating it becomes a major problem. Thus, prevention strategies are fundamental.

Sea piracy can therefore be defined as the criminal activities and illegal seizure of properties, attack and abduction of seafarers and vessels, takeover of ships, robbery and diversion of vessels for motives that may be personal, political or economic and which the repercussions have negative consequences on the travellers or passengers either within a shore of a country or in international waters (Hassan and Hassan, 2017). Sea piracy has been identified by the international security bodies as one of the major threats, not only to Nigeria national security, but to the international peace (IMB, 2009). Sea piracy is a robbery or forcible depreciation on the high seas, without lawful authority, *done animo furandi*, in the spirit and intention of universal hostility.

- a. It can also be seen as the act of forcefully taking over a ship or ships on the high sea with the intention to steal the cargo, take the passengers hostage or to commit murder. Piracy consists of any of the following acts:
- b. Any illegal act of violence or detention, or any act of depredation, committed for private ends by the crew or the passengers of a private ship or a private aircraft, and directed:
 - (i) On the high seas, against another ship or aircraft, or against persons or property on board such ship or aircraft;
 - (ii) Against a ship, aircraft, persons or property in a place outside the jurisdiction of any State; (b) any act of voluntary participation in the operation of a ship or of an aircraft with knowledge of facts making it a pirate ship or aircraft;
- (c) Any act of inciting or of intentionally facilitating an act described in subparagraph (a) or (b)

From the foregoing, sea piracy can be defined as a criminal act that involves maritime stealing, hostage taking, and disruption of economic, political, and social activities around the maritime domain. A mechanism is essential to eradicate piracy, it is utmost important to put up early preventive and warning strategies to prevent its escalation. The issue of piracy cannot be dealt with only by military might. They need multifarious and coordinated responses and tactical innovation. Piracy in Rivers State moreover forcefully reveals how apparently local problems have considerable global effects. Piracy security issues will consequently have to be understood as a dilemma requiring ongoing international consideration and action.

Concept of Socio-economic Development

According to Abuiyada (2018), development is underpinned by change, and change in this context means progress from one state of affairs to another state of affairs, which is vital in this paper. However, this definition of development did not meet our requirements in this paper because it did not specifically identify poverty and unemployment as indices of development. Neatu and Ciobanu (2014) noted that development is used to describe the level of improvement in the quality of lives of individuals in the areas of positive changes in housing quality, increase in the standard of living, freedom of expression,

improvement in the access to education, among others. Irrespective of the dimensions of development, individuals are its victims and beneficiaries. Though the author defined development as a positive change which is needed in this study, the definition did not specifically identify poverty and unemployment levels as indices of development as required in this paper. Therefore, development is defined in this paper as quantitative and qualitative changes involving reduction in unemployment and poverty levels in the coastal areas of Rivers States arising from mitigation of the nature of international maritime security threats plaguing coastal areas.

Litwinski (2017) defined socio-economic development as the kind of change that brings about improvement or increase in the resources of individuals in a state and decrease the degree of dependency of individuals in a state on the extended family system. Panth (2020) noted that socio-economic development is regarded as crucial to a state in reducing the level of poverty, provision of more employment, engendering higher incomes, improved goods and services as well as the use of the latest technology in production. It is accompanied by improvements in the level of infrastructure, and promotion of political, institutional and social factors that facilitate positive changes in the economy. The foregoing definition of socioeconomic development is related to this study since it incorporated poverty and employment as critical variables in the understanding of the concept, but the definition is not focused on coastal communities of Rivers States. For Bilgaev, Dong, Cheng, Sadykova, and Mikhova (2020), socioeconomic development cannot be defined without linking it to sustainable development, which means judicious utilisation of natural resources, growth of social as well as economic indicators and safeguarding of the lives of individuals. The author further stressed that socio-economic issues include inequality, poverty as well as issues relating to health, education, access to facilities and general improvement of people in the country. Therefore, socio-economic development is defined in this study as progressive reduction of poverty and unemployment levels, increase in quality education, improvement in health facilities, access to medical care, etc in the coastal areas of Rivers States through mitigation of international maritime security threats especially sea piracy and oil theft plaguing the coastal areas of the states.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research design was adopted by this study to gather information from the respondents on the issue under study. The study population consists of boat operators and waterways users around Rivers State. The study purposively selected five jetty locations which include Abonnema, Abuloma, Bonny, Okrika and ATC. Using random sampling method, fifty respondents from each of the selected routes were selected for the study, thus bringing the sample size to 250. The questionnaire was structured into two sections. Section A entails the demographic attributes while the Section B centred on questions used in testing the causes and impact of sea piracy and socioeconomic development. The responses were rated with strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. Data obtained were presented using tables while simple percentage was used to for data analysis.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Presentation of Data

Gender	Male		Female		Total	
Age	F	%	F	%	F	%
18 – 35	50	20	20	8	70	28
36 – 55	80	32	30	12	110	92
56 – Above	50	20	20	8	70	28
Total	180	72	70	28	250	100

Source: Field Work, 2024.

Table 1 above indicates that the respondents have different ages as classified by their gender. From the table above, respondent comprises 72% male and 28% female with their ages ranging from 18 – 35, 36 – 55 and 56 – above. This implies that majority of the respondents are male who have also spent a lot of years in sea business.

Table 2 Shows Educational qualification of Respondents

Gender Academic Background	Male		Female		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
SSCE	40	16	8	2	48	19.2
ND/NCE	50	20	20	8	70	28
BSC/HND/PGD	30	12	10	4	40	16
MSC/MBA/MPA	10	4	2	1.25	12	4.8
Others	50	20	30	12	80	32
Total	180	72	70	28	250	100

Source: Field Work, 2024.

The table above indicates the various academic qualification of respondents as well as their gender. It is revealed that majority of the respondents are male with 40:8 SSCE holders, 50:20 ND/NCE holders, 30:10 BSC/HND/PGD holders, 10:2 MSC/MBA/MPA holders and 50:30 others. This indicates that the respondents have good knowledge of the issue under investigation.

Research Question 1: *What are the causes of sea piracy in Rivers State?*

Table 3 Responses on the causes of sea pirate in Rivers State

Statement		SA	A	D	SD	Total	Agreement (%)
Sea piracy is a product of politicians to gain relevance in the political space of the state	F	110	50	40	50	250	64
	%	44	20	16	20	100	
Inordinate ambition to get rich quick has propelled the youths to get involve in sea piracy.	F	135	60	15	40	250	78
	%	54	24	6	16	100	
Marginalization and years of neglect by the government and IOCs contribute to the menace of sea pirates.	F	80	150	10	10	250	92
	%	32	60	4	4	100	

Source: Field Work, 2024.

The table above indicates the response rate and percentages of agreement in each statement. On whether sea piracy is a product of politicians to gain relevance in the political space of the state, 160 respondents making 64% of the respondents agreed that sea piracy is a product of politicians to gain relevance in the state. This indicates that sea piracy is an instrument used by politicians to gain relevance in the state. 195 respondents which represent 78% agreed that inordinate ambition to get rich quick has propelled the youths to get involved in sea piracy while 92% of the respondents agreed that marginalization and years of neglect by the government and IOCs contribute to the menace of sea pirates. Therefore, this paper deduced that politicians, inordinate ambition and many years of neglect by international oil companies and the government are significant causes of sea piracy in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *What is the impact of sea piracy in Socioeconomic Development?*

Table 4 Responses on the impact of sea piracy in Socioeconomic Development

Statement		SA	A	D	SD	Total	Agreement (%)
Reduce oil production and cost of energy	F	150	60	20	20	250	84
	%	60	24	8	8	100	
Kill sea businesses, scare workers, and causes loss of lives and property	F	75	135	30	10	250	84
	%	30	54	12	4	100	
Increases the cost of shipping and insurance of sea facilities, otherwise affect the economy negatively	F	80	99	41	30	250	71.6
	%	32	39.6	16.4	12	100	

Source: Field Work, 2024.

The responses gathered from the respondents as presented above indicates than more than 70% of the respondents are in agreement with all the items in the table to indicates the impact of sea piracy in socioeconomic development include: Reduce oil production and cost of energy (84%); Kill sea businesses, scare workers, and causes loss of lives and property (84%); and increases the cost of shipping and insurance of sea facilities, otherwise affect the economy negatively (71.6%).

Research Question 3: What is the socioeconomic effect of sea piracy in Rivers State?

Table 5 Responses on the socioeconomic effect of sea piracy in Rivers State

Statement		SA	A	D	SD	Total	Agreement (%)
Increases crime rate by introducing other criminal gangs into the nefarious business	F	110	50	40	50	250	64
	%	44	20	16	20	100	
Discourages sea travelling and cripple sea businesses	F	135	60	15	40	250	78
	%	54	24	6	16	100	
Endanger livelihoods by causing health challenge to dwellers and passengers, particularly when hostage taking is involved	F	80	150	10	10	250	92
	%	32	60	4	4	100	

Source: Field Work, 2024.

The responses gathered from the respondents as presented above indicates than more than 70% of the respondents are in agreement with all the items in the table to indicates the impact of sea piracy in socioeconomic development include: Increases crime rate by introducing other criminal gangs into the nefarious business (64%); Discourages sea travelling and cripple sea businesses (78%); and endanger livelihoods by causing health challenge to dwellers and passengers, particularly when hostage taking is involved (92%).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Causes of Sea Piracy in Socio-economic Development in Rivers State: Investigation reveals that sea piracy is a product of politicians to gain relevance in the political space of the state. This claim has been confirmed by 160 respondents making 64% of the respondents who agreed that sea piracy is a product of politicians to gain relevance in the political space of the state. Also, 195 respondents which represent 78% agreed that inordinate ambition to get rich quick has propelled the youths to get involved in sea piracy while 92% of the respondents agreed that marginalization and years of neglect by the government and IOCs contribute to the menace of sea pirates. The position has been affirmed by Sofiri, Nyiayaana, and Jack (2022) who claimed that Rivers State has been known for political instability. Most time, these politicians recruit these boys, most of whom are cultists to intimidate members of opposition political party to gain undue advantage over state affairs. An interviewee who corroborated the claim revealed that:

Sea piracy is the brainchild of politicians who use them to cause havoc during elections and when the elections are over, politicians are unable to curtail their excesses, guns cannot be retrieved, then they graduate from the lower level of crime and dip their hands into a higher version of business (sea piracy) that yields higher profits using the weapons purchased by these unscrupulous politicians (J. Nwidam, personal communication, June 2, 2024).

In reaction to the above, Joab-Peterside (2016) noted that the picture that emerges from sea piracy is an ideology which views politics as a form of war, in which the pursuit of power by the political class has led to a lack of respect for the formal rules governing party electoral competition, with competitive electoral politics assuming ruthless dimensions, based on zero-sum calculations, with the assumption that the winner wins all, and the loser loses all (Joab-Peterside and Zalik, 2009). Under such circumstances, instead of democracy being anchored on tolerance, moderation, fair play under the rule of law, and

respect for the sanctity of the electoral process, it has become a battle in which the political leadership and the masses of the people are increasingly engaged in violence-spinning fraudulent electoral practices. Central to this political culture which views electoral politics as a form of war is the creation and use of cult groups and militias by political parties in power either as part of their electioneering campaign arsenal or election control mechanism (Joab-Peterside, Porter and Watts, 2012).

Part of the problem derives from the harmful business and environmental practices of major oil companies operating in the area. It is, therefore, important that these companies have not live up to expectation to clean up oil spills and end gas flaring, neither do they support conservation, and environmental restoration activities in impacted communities. The neglect or marginalization over the years has contributed to the reason, sea pirates indulge in the nefarious business maritime crimes. Another respondent revealed that:

These companies most time feel reluctant to pay special compensation to communities devastated by environmental degradation occasioned by oil prospecting and exploitation. This has also led to regular protests from community members arising from the inaction and action of the multinational oil companies operating in the area. Sometimes, these protests resulted in a confrontation between state security forces and community members (H. Iyoha, personal communication, June 4, 2024).

From the above, it is deduced that the causes of sea piracy are numerous. According to Nwalozie (2020), the piracy problem in Nigeria ultimately links to the country's dysfunctional oil industry and the violent politics of the Niger Delta. Given that Nigeria is the world's eighth-largest producer of oil, unfortunately, it suffers from shortages of refined fuels (Economist 2014). Some see this as a problem created by some unpatriotic citizens seeking to stymie national progress and development. One of the significant causes of piracy is corruption, weak law enforcement and poverty (Ben-Ari, 2013). These causes suggest that the problem with piracy in Nigeria is traceable to the conspiracy with government officials. Similarly, Perouse de Montclos (2012), claims that some Navy, Customs and Ports Authority staff collude with the pirates by providing insider information, to unleash piracy and armed robbery on vessels navigating the high seas, in the hope to share the proceeds among the parties.

Impact of Sea Piracy on Socio-economic Development of Rivers State: The responses gathered from the respondents as presented above indicates than more than 70% of the respondents are in agreement with all the items in the table to indicates the impact of sea piracy in socioeconomic development include: Reduce oil production and cost of energy (84%); Kill sea businesses, scare workers, and causes loss of lives and property (84%); and increases the cost of shipping and insurance of sea facilities, otherwise affect the economy negatively (71.6%).

This has been affirmed also by Okoro, Asiagwu and Ejiofor (2021) that sea piracy has an impact on sea economic activities such as oil production and cost of energy, insurance and shipping costs, tourism and fishing. According to interviewee who responded reveals that:

Sea piracy has cost Nigeria oil production and cost of energy. During the period, oil production has reduced drastically which energy cost has been unimaginable. This has created adverse effect on maritime economy and the well-being of the people of the state. Okrika jetty was once known as an anchorage site for foreign vessels but today, the case is different. This is one reason; the refinery at a time does not receive crude oil through the pipeline. Crude oil transportation through the pipeline resume after the amnesty programme (t. Tamunoeli, personal communication, June 8, 2024).

Drew from above, threats to energy security from sea piracy are a concern. According to Okoro, Asiagwu and Ejiofor (2021), In November 2008, the Sirius Star carrying two million barrels of crude oil from Saudi Arabia to the United States (worth approximately \$100 million) became the largest oil tanker to be seized by pirates (Akinsanmi, 2010). It was held for two months until being released upon payment of a ransom. It is also revealed that sea piracy also imposes significant costs on local fishing economies. According to IMO, pirates attacked tuna vessels at least three times in 2009 as they fished 650 to 800 kilometers beyond the territorial waters. One vessel was captured, leading to a ransom payment that exceeded US\$1 million. The threat of pirate attacks has prompted many vessels to avoid some of the richest fishing spots in the ocean. Dwindling catches have raised concern that the state could face severe economic problems. The dramatic rise of piracy in the Gulf of Guinea is changing the insurance landscape. While piracy is not a new insured risk, the increase in pirate attacks along the Gulf has affected premiums and coverage. Ships which continue to pass through the Gulf have to purchase a war risk insurance coverage.

The findings of this study corroborate with Essien (2015) whose study indicated significant negative effect of pirate attacks on sea business operation. Also, the effect of sea robberies was obtained to be negative while sea security surveillance showed a significant positive effect on sea business operation. It also supports the study conducted by Osemwege (2019) whose study revealed that indigenous participation in the Nigerian Shipping industry was low due to some challenges. Some of the identified challenges include policy inconsistency, limited stakeholder involvement, sea piracy, inadequate capital investment and stringent credit facilities. Similarly, our finding reinforce Nwalozie (2020) study revealed that criminal activities like piracy have been a significant disadvantage to the development of the Nigerian maritime sector. More, the findings of this study are in alignment with Toakodi et al. (2019), whose study revealed that the activities of sea robbers have adverse effect on the number of international and domestic tourists as well as impact negatively on coastal and maritime tourism. Following from the above, huge cost of oil production, cost of energy, kill sea businesses, scare workers, and causes loss of lives and property and increases the cost of shipping and insurance of sea facilities are significant impact of sea piracy on socioeconomic development of Rivers State.

Socio-economic effect of Sea Piracy in Rivers State: Data analysis reveals that as sea pirate increases, it also increases crime rate by introducing other criminal gangs into the nefarious business which has been supported by 64% of the respondents. The study finds that sea piracy discourages sea travelling and cripple sea businesses by 78% of the respondents while 92% responded that it endangers livelihoods by causing health challenge to dwellers and passengers, particularly when hostage taking is involved. An interviewee responded that:

I became poor during the period of sea madness. My sea businesses all crumbled due to sea robbery. At a time, my son that was coming to visit us in the creek was kidnap. I sold all my belongings and investment to secure his release and since then it has not been the same (K. Wariboko, personal communication, June 10, 2024).

In line with the findings above, Agbai, Aliegba and Muhammed (2023) claimed that sea piracy largely increased job losses in the coastal areas while oil theft pose huge threats to the oil servicing jobs in coastal areas in the states. They opined that the implication of sea piracy and oil theft for economic development in Nigeria is that both crimes increase poverty in the coastal areas of Rivers States through job losses. In addition, oil theft and sea piracy negatively impact on the coastal areas of Rivers States by making some of the companies that provide ancillary services to major shipping companies in the area to shut down. This is connected to the fact that oil theft and sea piracy deprive people in the coastal areas of Rivers States the ability to adequately cater for their families in terms of reducing their access to education and healthcare facilities through increase in poverty level in the coastal areas.

In another view, Sofiri, Nyiayaana, and Jack (2022) noted that sea piracy is the most prevalent insecurity issue in coastal areas of the state like Andoni, Bonny, Bakana, Bille, Kula among others. Targets of sea

pirates are usually passenger boats, local market boats conveying foodstuff and consumables to coastal communities and local fishermen. Occupants of boats undersea pirates' attacks are usually robbed, kidnapped, raped, and sometimes murdered. In most cases, occupants of the boats are asked to disembark into the mangrove forests and sometimes into the river while the sea pirates dispossessed them of their valuables as well as the boats and engines, leaving them stranded in the swamps. Degema and Bonny LGAs have remained hotspots for sea piracy attacks. For instance, on the 16th of April, 2020, sea pirates with a speed boat engine of 200 horsepower attacked a vessel along the New Calabar River. Also, on April 6, 2020, a 12-seater passenger speed boat from Port Harcourt en-route Bakana was intercepted by sea pirates who robbed the occupants and made away with their boat while dumping them in the swamps. On December 8, 2019, eleven corpses were discovered in a boat by security agents patrolling the Jerusalem creek in Ke community. An assault rifle was discovered alongside the corpses and locals told newsmen that the victims were travellers killed by pirates. Sea pirates seized nineteen (19) expatriates on board a vessel loaded with Bonny Light crude oil in 2019. Similarly, two passenger boats were attacked simultaneously along the Bonny waterway, where passengers were robbed and two persons were abducted, including a serving councillor in the local government.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that violent acts at sea threaten security measures put in place to protect travellers and seafarers and any threat to maritime security can lead to financial losses from potential investors. Artisanal fishermen who invest a lot of money into their operations are left scarred psychologically, financially, physically and emotionally with robbery incidents at sea, making it difficult for them to return to fishing. Commercial traffic by boat operators has significantly decreased, as individuals who would have voyaged by water for job related purposes or to trade are terrified of being attacked by sea robbers who often aim for expatriates and other Nigerian workers in the Oil and Gas industry. This causes a reduction in investment ventures in that region since most investors are afraid to invest due to insecurity to life and business enterprises. The activities of sea robbers affect fishing business and other commercial activities as there is a decrease in the fleet of fishing trawlers on these waters thereby affecting fishermen and traders resulting to a huge loss of revenue.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the study therefore recommends the following;

- i. Efforts should be made to reform maritime policy to ensure that their activities are geared towards protecting life and property and not for selfish reasons.
- ii. Death penalty should be put forward for any pirate practices as part of sea policy as this will discourage terror and promote peace in the water ways
- iii. Government should see to the activities of oil producing firms and others to ensure that they carry out their corporate social responsibility in an equitable and peaceful manner without any form of conflict between and among oil companies and communities.

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